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Bovine Faecal Extracellular Vesicles: A novel non-invasive tool for understanding gut physiology and pathophysiology in calves

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ABSTRACT

Dairy calf gut health is linked with the development and future production. Fecal extracellular vesicles (fEVs) have emerged as a non-invasive tool in elucidating gut physiology and pathophysiology. Being a complex matrix, enrichment of extracellular vesicles (EVs) from ruminant/pre-ruminant feces is difficult. Nevertheless, if enriched, they have great potential as a gut health diagnostic and monitoring tool in dairy calves. Therefore, this study aimed to devise a protocol to enrich and characterize fEVs from pre-weaned calves. We developed a fEV enrichment method by combination of differential centrifugation and double size exclusion chromatography and then characterized the fEVs from the healthy calves. The study also assessed sample storage conditions, and the results indicated that storing pre-processed fecal samples at -80°C effectively preserves EVs without introducing additional nanoparticles. Finally, fEVs from 10 d old healthy and *Cryptosporidium* spp. positive calves were enriched and a comparative analysis of fEV characteristics between the 2 groups was performed. Characterization results on EVs specific protein biomarkers, size profile, total protein content, zeta potential, and morphology clearly established the enrichment of fEVs with the developed protocol. *Cryptosporidium* spp. positive and negative calves fEV analysis revealed a significant decrease in average nanoparticle size and AU: zeta potential values in AU:*Cryptosporidium* spp. infected calves. Furthermore, the enriched fEV carried protein and nucleic acid cargo which could be further analyzed for other biomarkers to predict the gut physiology and pathophysiology of calves. In conclusion, our study has

successfully optimized a protocol to enrich high purity grade EVs from calf feces and displayed potential diagnostic application as a non-invasive tool.

Keywords: Calf faeces, extracellular vesicles, *Cryptosporidium*, disease diagnosis and monitoring

INTRODUCTION

Gut health is linked with the development and production of farm animals. A comprehensive understanding of the early host-gut pathogens interactions can facilitate disease prevention, identification of biomarkers for early diagnosis, prognosis, and monitoring of diseases. Plethora of techniques have been developed enabling the accurate identification of gut pathogens and their associated health conditions at different stages of infection (Jean Beltran et al., 2017; Oeschger et al., 2021). Identification of disease-specific biomarkers at the earliest host-pathogen communications interphase may not be feasible with the existing sample type and detection methods, especially during the early asymptomatic sub-clinical stage. Particularly, gastric infections caused by different pathogens increases the mortality and morbidity of pre-weaned calves, especially during the transition period of the development of acquired immune response. Predominant infections identified in pre-weaned calves with gastric problems are *Cryptosporidium*, *Giardia*, rotavirus, coronavirus, salmonella, and *E. coli* (Niine et al., 2018). Although established laboratory diagnosis methods are available for identifying infectious diseases, precise methods are needed to understand the host-pathogen interactions that are crucial in the prevention, treatment, and prognosis of diseases.

Extracellular vesicles (EVs) are emerging as novel candidates for understanding host-pathogen interactions (Lécrivain and Beckmann, 2020; Rueter and Bielaszewska, 2020). They play a crucial role in mediating not only in intercellular communication but also in inter-

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species, and cross-kingdom communication (Correa et al., 2020). EVs are lipid bi-membrane-enclosed, highly heterogeneous vesicles secreted by most cell types during physiological, and pathological conditions that transfer functional cargo to the recipient cells (Regev-Rudzki et al., 2021). According to their size, mechanisms of biogenesis, and secretion, the International Society for Extracellular Vesicles (ISEV) categorizes EVs as exosomes, microvesicles, and apoptotic bodies (Welsh et al., 2024).

Feces are heavily exposed to the gastrointestinal environment and this makes it a comprehensive reflection of the gut. Therefore, feces could be used to study gastrointestinal (GI) physiology, and pathophysiology, as well as diagnose and monitor the diseases (Grego et al., 2022). Fecal extracellular vesicles (fEVs) have emerged as a promising tool for monitoring gut health and disease diagnosis. fEVs contain a diverse array of biomolecules that can be used in the diagnosis and monitoring of GI diseases (Kaisanlahti et al., 2023; Rodríguez-Díaz et al., 2023). Recent findings suggest that certain bacteria in the fecal microbiome release EVs, potentially playing a role in inducing intestinal permeability as part of early gut infections (Rodríguez-Díaz et al., 2023). As per the Trojan exosome hypothesis, scientific literature indicates that host-pathogen interaction manipulates the host's exosome biosynthetic machinery, leading to the secretion of exosomes AU: encapsulating infectious particles (Ip-inmoroti and Matthews, 2020). Currently, no published reports exist regarding fEVs enrichment from ruminant/pre-ruminant feces. Developing an EV-based tool will aid in understanding the complex dynamics of host-pathogen interactions and early diagnosis, prognosis, and monitoring of infectious diseases (Schorey et al., 2015).

EVs carry a wide range of cellular components as their cargo including proteins, nucleic acids, lipids, and metabolites. These cargo molecules can mediate the cellular communication between parent cells and recipient cells (Sivanantham and Jin, 2022; Kumar et al., 2024). A cargo analysis of fEVs has also identified disease-specific patterns and detected changes reflecting disease progression or response to treatment (Schou et al., 2020; Garcia et al., 2023). However, protein, DNA, and RNA associated with isolated EVs have not yet been studied specifically for diagnosing or monitoring of infectious gut diseases and pathogens.

Cryptosporidiosis, a parasitic infection caused by the *Cryptosporidium* spp, poses a substantial global challenge, affecting both humans and livestock by primarily affecting the gastrointestinal system and leading to millions of reported diseased cases each year (Robertson et al., 2014; ECDC, 2019; Santoro et al., 2019). Therefore, in the present study, we investigated the potential application of fEVs in understanding gut pathophysiology, particularly in the context of infectious diseases, with

specific attention to *Cryptosporidium* infections in calves as an example, and we also aim to investigate the potential utility of fEVs in developing them as a non-invasive tool to study gut physiology and pathophysiology.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Animals and ethical clearance

All experiments involving animals were approved by the Ethical Committee of Animal Experiments of the Estonian Ministry of Agriculture (animal project permit no. 116). Female calves included in this study were all from the same dairy farm located in South-East-Estonia. Calves were separated from their mothers immediately after birth and weighed on a digital scale. They received 3 L of unpasteurized colostrum within the first 2 h following their birth. Colostrum was collected from the dam and the quality was examined visually and with a hydrometer (Kruuse colostrum densimeter, Jørgen Kruuse A/S, Langeskov, Denmark). In the event of unsatisfactory colostrum quality, deep frozen colostrum from an alternate dam was provided. Furthermore, the calves were also fed 3–4 kg of warmed unpasteurized raw milk twice per day with free access to hay and starter feed (Prestarter, Agrovarustus OÜ, Tartu, Estonia) up to 15–17 d of age. AU: Fecal samples from the calves naturally infected with *Cryptosporidium* and non-infected were taken at 10 d of age to study the differences in fEVs between naturally infected and non-infected calves. For determining the effect of storage conditions on enrichment and characteristics of fEVs, fresh fecal samples were collected from clinically healthy 2-week old calves from the same farm.

Sample collection, initial laboratory analyses and study design

Initially, 62 fecal samples from 10 d old female calves were collected directly from the rectum using sterile techniques and immediately transported to the laboratory on ice. Calves did not receive any prophylactic anti-*Cryptosporidium* treatment. The fecal samples were then subjected to standard diagnostic tests to detect infections: *Cryptosporidium* spp. and *Giardia* spp. infections were diagnosed employing an immunofluorescence staining method (Crypto/Giardia Cel, Cellabs Pty Ltd., Sydney, Australia) adhering to the manufacturer's instructions. The results were measured as the approximate number of oocysts per gram of fecal matter (opg) in AU: *Cryptosporidium* and as number of cysts in *Giardia* described by Niine et al., (2018). Presence of rotavirus, bovine coronavirus (BCV) and AU:*Escherichia coli* F5 attachment factor (as a marker of enterotoxigenic *E. coli*)

were also tested using an antigen detecting ELISA kit (BIO K 348 – Multiscreen AgELISA Calf digestive, Bio-X Diagnostics S.A Rochefort, Belgium) according to the manufacturer's guidelines.

Following the initial analyses, 6 fecal samples were randomly selected to optimize the method for isolating EVs from calf feces and characterization of fEVs. All selected samples were tested negative for *Cryptosporidium* spp., *Giardia* spp., rotavirus, and AU:*E. coli* infections. The enrichment of fEVs was performed using a 2-step protocol consisting of sample pre-processing followed by size exclusion chromatography (SEC). Enriched fEVs were characterized by nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA), Bradford assay, Western blotting and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Following the isolation and characterization of fEVs, molecular cargo associated with fEVs including protein, DNA, and RNA were analyzed. The overall experimental design for fEV enrichment, characterization and molecular cargo analysis are depicted in the supplementary figure S1.

The 4 fresh samples collected for determining the effect of storage conditions on enrichment and characteristics of fEVs were aliquoted into 3 groups that contained 0.5 g of feces from each batch. The groups were subjected to different conditions.

Group I. The fresh feces were immediately subjected to pre-processing and the fEVs were enriched. Enriched fEVs were immediately characterized by performing NTA and TEM analysis.

Group II. The fecal samples were stored at -80°C after pre-processing (sequential centrifugation and filtered through $0.45\ \mu\text{m}$ filters described in 2.3.1) and without isolating EVs.

Group III. The fecal samples were stored at -80°C without pre-processing.

After a storage period of 90 d at -80°C , samples of groups II and III were thawed on ice, and fEVs were isolated continuing the aforementioned protocol. The characteristics of the enriched fEVs from these 2 groups were analyzed by employing NTA and TEM.

Twelve fecal samples were randomly selected for isolating and characterizing fEVs in 2 groups based on the amount of *Cryptosporidium* spp. oocysts. These groups were: healthy ($n = 6$)-no oocysts found, and *Cryptosporidium* spp. infected ($n = 6$)-median number of oocysts per gram of feces measuring 7.43×10^5 and in the range of 7.75×10^4 to 9.02×10^6 opg. All these animals were free of *Giardia* spp, rotavirus, BCV and *E. coli*. All these 12 fecal samples were stored at -80°C until isolation and characterization of fEVs. The fecal EVs were isolated following the optimized method. Then, these EVs were characterized as described earlier.

Fecal extracellular vesicle (fEV) isolation

Sample pre-processing. Fecal samples (0.5 g) were dissolved in 10 mL of Dulbecco's phosphate-buffered saline without Ca^{+2} and Mg^{+2} (DPBS, Verviers, Belgium) and mixed on a tube rotator for an hour at 4°C . Samples were preprocessed by a series of sequential centrifugations, as mentioned by AU: Midekessa et al. (2020) with slight modifications. Briefly, the fecal suspensions were centrifuged at $300 \times g$ for 10 min at 4°C to remove the undissolved particles. The pellets were discarded and the supernatants were used for another round of centrifugation at $400 \times g$ for 10 min to remove cells. The resultant supernatants were centrifuged again at $4000 \times g$ for 10 min to remove any remaining cell debris. Finally, to further remove the particles that lie within the range of the apoptotic bodies, supernatants from the previous step were centrifuged at $10,000 \times g$ for 10 min. Afterward, the supernatant was filtered through polyethersulfone $0.45\ \mu\text{m}$ filter (Minisart syringe filter, Gottingen, Germany) before concentrating it for further purification.

Size exclusion chromatography (SEC). Preprocessed fecal suspensions were concentrated to $500\ \mu\text{L}$ using Amicon® Ultra-15 centrifugal filter (10 kDa cut-off, Merck Millipore Ltd., Darmstadt, Germany). The fEVs were isolated from concentrated fecal suspensions by utilizing SEC. A cross-linked 4% agarose matrix of $90\ \mu\text{m}$ beads (Sepharose 4 fast flow, GE HealthCare Bio-Sciences AB, Uppsala, Sweden) in a 10 cm gravity column (Econo-Pac® Chromatography columns, Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA, USA) was used, and PBS was used as the mobile phase as described previously (Midekessa et al., 2020). Briefly, the elute was collected into 20 fractions each containing $500\ \mu\text{L}$. The fractions no. 4 to 11 obtained after the first step of SEC (sSEC) were selected based on NTA analysis and Bradford assay as the fractions with the highest number of nanoparticles with a minimal amount of protein. Selected fractions were concentrated again to $500\ \mu\text{L}$ using Amicon® Ultra-2 mL centrifugal filters (Merck Millipore Ltd., Darmstadt, Germany, 10 kDa cut-off) and passed through a new SEC column for the second time (dSEC). The elute was again collected into 20 fractions of $500\ \mu\text{L}$. The fractions 5 to 9 with high EV numbers and negligible protein contamination were again selected based on the data obtained from NTA analysis and Bradford assay. These fractions were concentrated to $500\ \mu\text{L}$.

Characterization of fEVs.

Nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA) and zeta potential (ZP) Concentrations and sizes of nanoparticles in each fraction were measured with NTA ZetaView® (PMX 110 V3.0 instrument by Particle Metrix GmbH, Inning am Ammersee, Germany, software version 8.05.14

SP7) coupled with ZetaView NTA software for data analysis. The operating instructions of the manufacturer were followed as described in the literature (Dissanayake et al., 2021). The auto-alignment of the instrument was performed using 100 nm polystyrene particle size standards (Applied Microspheres B.V., Leusden, Netherlands, Catalogue no. 10100). The samples were measured in the scatter mode for estimation of the total particle concentration and size profiles using the following settings: camera sensitivity 85, shutter 70, frame rate 30 frames per second (fps), number of cycles 3, and number of frames 11.

The zeta potential of enriched EVs were measured using ZetaView PMX 110 as described in previous studies (Midekessa et al., 2020; Dissanayake et al., 2021). In brief, pH of the EV samples was adjusted to pH 7.0. The zeta potential was assessed at 22°C under the following settings: cycles 5, sensitivity 85, shutter speed 70, and frame rate at 30 frames per second.

Protein quantification AU: Bradford assay was used to determine the soluble protein concentration of each fraction collected after the SEC, in accordance with the methodology described by Piibor et al. (2023a). A dilution series of bovine serum albumin (BSA) standard solution (2 mg/mL, Sigma-Aldrich, AU: St Louis, MO, USA) was used to develop the standard curve ranging from 1.4 to 0.125 mg/mL. PBS was used as a negative control. The absorbance of the standards and the samples were measured with a spectrophotometer (Ledetect 96 Microplate Reader; Biomed Dr. Wieser GmbH, Salzburg, Austria) at 620 nm wavelength and the protein concentrations of each of the fractions were calculated.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) Morphological evaluation of fEVs were carried out by employing TEM as described previously (Piibor et al., 2023a). In brief, 20 µL of EV suspension was placed on formvar/carbon-coated 200 mesh grids (Agar Scientific, Stansted, UK). The EVs were allowed to adsorb on the grid for 20 min. Afterward, the same grids were incubated with 2% uranyl acetate (Polysciences, Warrington, PA, USA) for 5 min and air-dried to obtain contrasted images of EVs. The EVs were visualized using JEM 1400 TEM (JEOL Ltd. Tokyo, Japan, with Morada TEM CCD camera, Olympus, Hamburg, Germany) at 80 kV. The digital images of EV were captured using a numeric camera (Morada TEM CCD camera, Olympus, Hamburg, Germany)

Western blot analysis Western blot analysis was performed to confirm the presence of EV specific protein markers in the samples as described by (Piibor et al., 2023b). In brief, fecal supernatants collected after the preprocessing step and enriched fEVs were lysed in RIPA buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) supplemented with proteinase inhibitors (cat. 535140, EMD Millipore Corp., Burlington, MA, USA).

The total protein concentration of the lysed samples was quantified by the standard Bradford assay as described previously (Piibor et al., 2023b). The samples were normalized for the total protein concentration, denatured at 95°C for 10 min. The proteins were separated by SDS-PAGE in 12% acrylamide gel and transferred on to a 0.45 µm polyvinylidene difluoride (PVDF) membrane. The PVDF membrane was blocked with 5% nonfat milk (wt/vol, in PBST 0.05% Tween-20, Thermo Scientific, Michigan, USA) for 1 h at room temperature. Afterward, the membranes were incubated with primary antibodies of polyclonal anti-rabbit TSG 101 (AV38773–100UL, Sigma-Aldrich, Missouri, USA) at 1:1000, monoclonal mouse anti-Bovine CD 63 antibody clone CC25 (BIO-RAD MCA2042GA) at 1:1000, polyclonal anti-rabbit Calnexin antibody (NB100–1965, Novus Biologicals, USA) at 1:5000, polyclonal anti-rabbit β-actin (20536–1-AP, Proteintech Group Inc., 275 Rosemont, IL, USA) at 1:1000, and monoclonal anti-mouse Alix (sc-53540, Santa Cruz Biotechnology, CA, USA) at 1:1000 for overnight at 4°C. After the washing steps, membranes were incubated for one hour at room temperature with horseradish peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit secondary antibody (G21234, 1:20,000, Invitrogen, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Eugene, OR, USA) and goat anti-mouse secondary antibody (G21040, 1:20,000, Invitrogen, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Eugene, OR, USA). The protein bands were detected using Enhanced Chemiluminescence (ECL) Select Western Blotting Detection Reagent (GE Healthcare, Buckinghamshire, UK) in an imager with a capturing software (ImageQuant RT ECL Imager, GE Healthcare, Buckinghamshire, UK).

Identifying the biomolecules carried as cargo by EVs

Qualitative analysis of fEV-protein The enriched fEVs and fecal suspension were lysed in RIPA buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) supplemented with proteinase inhibitors (cat. 535140, EMD Millipore Corp., Burlington, MA, USA) and separated by 12% SDS-PAGE as described previously. The gel was stained in the Coomassie brilliant blue (CBB) solution (0.1% Coomassie blue in 10% acetic acid, 50% methanol) and shaken at room temperature for the duration of 1 h. Afterward, the gels were destained for 2 h in a destaining solution (10% acetic acid, 50% methanol AU: in water).

Isolation and quantification of fEV-DNA The fEV samples stored at –80°C were thawed on ice and divided into 2 equal volumes of 100 µL. One portion was subjected to treatment with DNase I (ThermoFisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) followed by incubation at 37°C for 30 min to remove DNA present on corona of EVs as well the EV-free DNA as described in previous studies (Fischer et al., 2016). The reaction of DNase I was terminated

by adding 0.5 M EDTA followed by incubation at 70°C for 10 min. The DNA isolation from another portion of the sample was performed without DNase I treatment and the sample volumes were equalized using nuclease-free water. Subsequently, the DNA was extracted using QIAamp DNA Micro Kit (Qiagen, cat no: 56304) and the quantification of DNA was performed using Qubit double stranded-DNA (dsDNA) Quantification Assay Kit (cat no: Q32851, AU: Life Technologies, Carlsbad, California, USA) and the Qubit 2.0 fluorometer AU: (Life Technologies).

By performing targeted PCR, we further investigated the DNA associated with fEV from different origins/sources. Such as the host, bacteria, nematodes, and plant material in the animal diet using specific primer sets to amplify distinct genetic regions of genomic DNA from different species. (Supplementary table S1). Green plant targeted gene amplification was conducted in parallel on the DNA isolated from fEVs of dairy cows. The same optimized method was followed to isolate fEVs and fEV-DNA from dairy cows.

Total RNA extraction, qualitative and quantitative analysis RNA was extracted from 100 μ L of enriched fEVs using the Qiagen miRNeasy Mini Kit (Germantown, MD, AU: USA) following the manufacturer's instructions. The quantity and quality of the extracted RNA samples were analyzed by Bioanalyzer Automated Electrophoresis instrument (Agilent technologies, Santa Clara, CA AU:, USA) using Agilent RNA 6000 Pico Kit (Agilent Technologies, cat. No. 5067–1513) (Northrop-Albrecht et al., 2022).

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis of NTA measurements were performed using R studio (R-4.1.2) and the data were presented as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). Mann-Whitney U test was used to analyze nanoparticle concentration, size, ZP, and total particle concentration. The differences between sSEC and dSEC isolated EVs samples, healthy and infected groups were assessed with 2-way ANOVA with posthoc Tukey multiple comparison tests for intergroup comparisons. The statistical significance was set at $P \leq 0.05$ and the graphs were generated with the GraphPad prism 8.0.1.

EV-TRACK

We have submitted all relevant data of our experiments to the EV-TRACK knowledgebase (EV-TRACK ID: EV240199) (Van Deun J, et al., 2017)

RESULTS

EVs size and concentration analysis of the fEV enriched fractions obtained from size exclusion chromatography columns

The different SEC elution fractions from the samples of calves free from *Cryptosporidium* spp., *Giardia* spp., rotavirus, BCV and enterotoxigenic *E. coli* infections were used in the initial analysis. The NTA revealed that in sSEC, fractions 4 to 11 displayed higher numbers of particles whereas fractions 5 to 9 from dSEC demonstrated the highest number of particles. AU: Furthermore, the protein assay results revealed that the EV-enriched fractions had minimal to no soluble proteins presence (Figure 1A, Figure 1B). Additionally, the particle size distribution in both groups was in the same range from 50 to 450 nm (Figure 1C). The total particle concentration, obtained through sSEC and dSEC were 3.62×10^{11} particles/mL and 3.02×10^{11} particles/mL respectively and not statistically different ($P < 0.05$). The incorporation of an additional SEC step in dSEC resulted in a decrease in the total particle concentrations of each fraction. However, the differences attained were not statistically significant (Figure 1D). Furthermore, the average nanoparticle size of the particles isolated utilizing sSEC and dSEC methods did not exhibit statistical significance, with the measurements of sSEC: 215.68 ± 4.68 nm and dSEC: 225.54 ± 5.67 nm (Figure 1E). Moreover, zeta potential analysis of isolated particles from both groups revealed no statistically significant difference, with values of -27.37 ± 0.50 mV for sSEC and -26.52 ± 0.31 mV for dSEC respectively (Figure 1F).

Morphological and biochemical characterization of fEVs

AU: The TEM images revealed the presence of characteristic EV structures in compliance with the previously described EVs by (Welsh et al., 2024). The EVs observed under TEM ranged in size from 50 to 450 nm. Notably, TEM images of particles obtained from the dSEC displayed a clean background with less artifacts compared with the sSEC enriched samples (Figure 2A, 2B).

Western blot analysis was performed according to the guidelines established by ISEV AU: Welsh et al. (2024). Notably, CD63 and TSG101 proteins were detected exclusively in the EV samples, while they were absent in the neat (unpurified) fecal suspension confirming the enrichment of the EVs in the fractions. Conversely, calnexin expression was observed only in the fecal suspension, indicating the absence of plasma protein contaminants in both EV fractions obtained through sSEC and dSEC methods. Furthermore, β -actin was included as a protein

loading control to ensure equal protein loading across samples (Figure 2C).

Analysis of fEV cargo

In this study, we aimed to quantify the total DNA present in the EV fractions derived from feces. First, we quantified the DNA isolated from the EV fractions without DNase I treatment to determine the total DNA quantity which represents the EV-free DNA as well as DNA encapsulated within fEVs. The quantity of total double-stranded DNA (dsDNA) was 2.52 ± 0.64 ng per 1×10^9 of fEVs. Subsequently, to specifically quantify the DNA encapsulated within fecal EVs, the EV enriched fraction underwent DNase I enzyme treatment before the DNA isolation. The quantity of encapsulated dsDNA within fEVs was 1.28 ± 0.39 ng per 1×10^9 EVs. To examine the DNA cargo content of fEVs, PCR was utilized to amplify genes specific to different species including the host (*Bos taurus*), bacteria, animal diet (green plants), and parasitic nematodes. The PCR findings in Figure 5A revealed a lack of amplification for the targeted genes associated with plant DNA and parasitic nematode DNA. However, successful amplification was observed for the host-targeted genes (119 base pairs) and bacteria-targeted gene (444 base pairs). Notably, this negative amplification for plant DNA was not only observed in fEV-DNA enriched from calf feces, but also in the fEV-DNA enriched from dairy cows using the same fEV isolation method (Figure 3B). Furthermore, the quantity and size distribution of RNA derived from fEVs (fEV-RNA) were assessed. According to the results, RNA concentration in 14 μ L of elute was 163.53 ± 57.17 pg/ μ L, and in total 2.29 ± 0.80 ng of RNA was yielded per 1×10^9 number of EVs. Considering the size distribution of fEV-RNA (Figure 3C), the predominant fragments were in the size range of 35 to 170 nucleotides. The results of SDS-PAGE analysis exhibited the total protein profile of fEVs (Figure 3D).

Fecal EVs can be successfully isolated from feces following short-term storage at -80°C

To investigate the effect of storage conditions on EVs, the characteristics of isolated fEVs from fresh feces (group I) were compared with feces stored after pre-processing (group II) and stored without pre-processing at -80°C (group III) were compared. This comparison revealed that the characteristics of fEVs isolated from group I and group II samples stored at -80°C were not significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Notably, a significant increase ($P = 0.028$) was observed in the total nanoparticle concentration in the EV fractions isolated from feces stored at -80°C without subjecting to preprocessing step (5.33×10^{11} particles/mL) in comparison to the EV frac-

tions isolated from fresh feces (2.48×10^{11} particles/mL) and stored samples after pre-processing (2.68×10^{11} particles/mL). However, there was no significant difference in the average size of nanoparticles between the groups ($P < 0.05$). AU: The TEM images revealed consistent observation of identical EVs across all 3 experimental groups (Figure 4).

Characterization of isolated fEVs from healthy and infected samples

The NTA of enriched fEVs revealed that fractions 5 to 9 were enriched with nanoparticles in both groups (Figure 5A). The particle size range for fEVs isolated from the healthy groups was found to be 50 to 350 nm, whereas the infected groups displayed a size distribution ranging from 50 to 300 nm (Figure 5B). There was no significantly different ($P = 0.760$) in total particles concentration between the healthy group (4.6×10^{11} particles/AU: mL) and the infected group (3.95×10^{11} particles/AU: mL) (Figure 5C). However, significant differences were observed between the 2 groups in terms of average nanoparticle size and zeta potential. The average size (diameter) of fEVs isolated from the infected group measured 150.19 ± 3.83 nm, which was significantly smaller compared with the size observed in the healthy group 172.62 ± 6.54 nm ($P = 0.015$) (Figure 5D). Furthermore, the zeta potential (ZP) of the infected group exhibited a significant decrease, with a value of -23.80 ± 0.71 mV, compared with the healthy group's ZP value of -26.36 ± 0.23 mV ($P = 0.028$) (Figure 5E).

DISCUSSION

Proper gut physiology of dairy calves at very young age is a critical factor influencing development, future production and reproduction performances. Since calves being very delicate and vulnerable at very young stage, non-invasive biological samples like feces, can offer significant potential for understanding gut physiology and diagnosing gastrointestinal diseases (Rodríguez-Díaz et al., 2023). Feces may contain EVs secreted by the host, gut microbiome, and gut parasites in addition to the EVs derived from diet. Even though the prior studies have demonstrated the methods to isolate EVs from human and mouse feces, there is no reported protocol to enrich and characterize ruminant/pre-ruminant fEVs (Yang et al., 2020; Rodríguez-Díaz et al., 2023). In the present study, we improvised a method to enrich more pure fEVs from pre-weaning and characterize them following the guidelines set by the ISEV. Additionally, we examined the impact of short-term storing of samples at -80°C on isolation and characteristics of fEV. To prove the potential of utilizing fEVs as a non-invasive diag-

Figure 1. Physical characterization of extracellular vesicles (EVs) enriched from calf feces. EVs were enriched using single size-exclusion chromatography (sSEC) and double size-exclusion chromatography (dSEC). Elution profile shows the nanoparticle concentration and soluble protein concentration in EV fractions enriched by (A) sSEC, and (B) dSEC, (C) size distribution profile of fEVs enriched from both sSEC and dSEC (D) total nanoparticle concentration of fEVs obtained by sSEC and dSEC (E) average size (diameter) of the fEVs enriched using sSEC and dSEC (F) zeta potential of particles measured by nanoparticle tracking analysis for both sSEC and dSEC. The data is presented as the mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM) ($n = 6$).

Figure 2. Characterization of fEVs using transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and Western blotting (n = 4). AU: (A) TEM images of fEVs. The magnified part of the image zoomed in to an individual EV exhibiting identical shapes of EVs. TEM also revealed the higher background artifacts/contaminants present in (A) sSEC enriched fEVs as compared with (B) dSEC enriched fEVs. (C) EVs purified from feces show expression of CD63, β-actin, TSG 101, and Calnexin in fEVs isolated by sSEC, and fEVs isolated by dSEC was demonstrated by Western blot analysis. AU: Lines 1 and 3 represent the fecal suspension, 2- fEVs enriched by sSEC, and 3- fEVs enriched by dSEC.

nosis, prognosis, and monitoring tool for GI infectious diseases, fEV characteristics from both healthy animals and *Cryptosporidium* infected animals were studied.

Several intestinal pathogens including *Cryptosporidium* spp., *Giardia* spp., rotavirus, BCV and enterotoxigenic *E. coli* could be responsible for the diagnosis of diarrhea in calves. In the protocol optimization phase of the investigations, we ensured that all the animals were devoid of infections during sample collection through laboratory analysis to maintain sample consistency. We employed differential centrifugation with SEC including certain modifications as the primary fEV enrichment technique for our current study. An additional step of SEC was introduced to enhance the purity of isolated fEVs. Introducing a second SEC step had no significant impact on EV numbers while improving the purity which is a key for biomarker discovery pipelines. Tulkens et al. (2020) have proved the significance of combining 2 or more techniques to enhance the purity of isolated EVs. Furthermore, according to previous studies, dSEC was effective in enriching EVs from human plasma and urine with minimal LDL and other soluble proteins in the EV fractions (Jung et al., 2021; Pinheiro et al., 2024). This is further confirmed by the depletion of soluble protein contamination and appearing less artifacts in TEM analy-

sis in EV-rich fractions obtained from sSEC compared with dSEC. Therefore, we can suggest that the optimized method for EV enrichment from calf feces can be easily employed to isolate EVs with negligible contaminants.

AU: The size distribution of the nanoparticles indicated the heterogeneity of vesicles present in isolated samples (Kamińska et al., 2023). In TEM analysis, the double membranous EV population exhibited the typical EV shape (Welsh et al., 2024). The size of EVs assessed by TEM analysis (approximately 50–450 nm) confirmed the size heterogeneity of EVs observed in the NTA analysis. The EVs enriched from both optimized protocols were in the same size range. Fecal-derived EVs can be co-isolated with bacterial pili and flagella because of their density and size (Tulkens et al., 2020). Similarly, morphologically similar structures to bacterial pili and flagella described in Tulkens et al., 2020 were found in our fEVs samples this could be observed in the electron microscopy image (Figures 3A and 3B). Since calf gut has active bacterial population even at young stage, there is a high potential to find bacterial debris overlapped with calf fecal-derived EVs. The amplification of bacterial genes in fEV derived DNA confirmed the presence of bacterial derived components presence in the enriched

Figure 5. Nanoparticle tracking analysis and zeta potential data of fEVs derived from feces of healthy ($n = 6$) and *Cryptosporidium* infected calves ($n = 6$). (A) fEVs in 20 fractions isolated by dSEC method, (B) size distribution of nanoparticles, (C) total nanoparticle concentration (D) average particle size and (E) zeta potential of particles isolated from healthy and cryptosporidium infected groups respectively. The data is presented as the mean \pm SEM (*, $P < 0.05$).

Figure 3. Analysis of fEV cargo. (A) PCR amplification of EV-derived DNA by targeting host-Cytochrome-b, bacteria-16S rRNA, plant-chloroplast-based rubisco (*rbcL*), and parasitic nematode-ITS 2 genes], (B) PCR amplification of *rbcL* gene for (a) cow and (b) calf fEV-DNA (C) Bioanalyzer -based electropherogram shows the size distribution of RNA fragments extracted from fEVs (D) Protein profiles analyzed by SDS-PAGE using Coomassie Brilliant Blue G250 staining, comparing (a) crude fecal suspension and (b) fEVs. (n = 4).

fEVs. This indicates the possible use of fEV derived DNA sequencing for bacterial diversity studies in the gut.

Physical properties such as the zeta potential of EVs are important in predicting the biological functions and colloidal stability in the different solutions that are used in various assays. Nanoparticles with a zeta potential value of -10 mV to $+10$ mV are known as electrically neutral particles that can easily form aggregations. The stability of nanoparticles is influenced not only by their ZP but also by environmental factors such as pH and ionic concentration (Midekessa et al., 2020). However, the particles with higher ZP values are more stable in solutions and they have a high potential to interact with

targeted cells (Akagi et al., 2014; Jamaludin et al., 2019). AU: The ZP values of enriched fEVs by optimized method indicate the better stability at pH 7. Therefore, this observation explains that fEVs enriched from calf feces have a great potential to be uptaken by target cells.

The purity of EVs are measured using standard protein markers. One such marker, calnexin, is an endoplasmic reticulum-associated protein is typically released by damaged cells and calnexin should not be detected in purified EV samples (Northrop-Albrecht et al., 2022). Based on the results obtained by Western blot, none of the isolated EV samples demonstrated any cellular impurities as evidenced by the lack of calnexin. Addition-

Figure 4. Characteristics of EVs isolated from fresh and stored samples. (A) Total particle concentration, (B) average particle size, (C) transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images of isolated fEVs from freshly collected fecal samples, (D) TEM images of isolated fEVs from fecal suspension stored for 90 d at -80°C after pre-processing and (E) TEM images of isolated fEVs from crude feces stored for 90 d at -80°C . The data is presented as the mean \pm SEM, $n = 4$ (*, $P < 0.05$).

ally, confirmation of fEV enrichment was achieved by detecting the expression of tetraspanins (surface markers of EVs) (Kagota et al., 2019), and Tumor Susceptibility Gene 101 protein (internal markers of EVs) (Linxweiler and Junker, 2020) exclusively in fEVs enriched fractions, rather than in fecal suspension. This observation aligns with the criteria outlined for the biochemical characterization of EVs by ISEV (Welsh et al., 2024).

In the current study, we successfully demonstrated the presence of DNA, protein, and RNA cargo in the enriched fEVs. The utilization of EV-based DNA for genomic studies or 16s RNA based sequencing aimed at identifying microbial diversity and tracing the EV origin are intriguing areas of further research. We quantified the DNA present in enriched fEV samples both before and after the DNase 1 enzyme treatment. The reduction of DNA quantity after the DNase 1 treatment suggests that EV samples isolated from calf feces can carry EV-free DNA in the corona and this finding aligns with the study by (Jin et al., 2016) which described the presence

of external DNA in serum-derived EV samples. Thus, by using gene-specific PCR, we showed that intact DNA cargo can be found in enriched fEVs. This is very important in terms of analysis of microbiota diversity studies concerning the dysbiosis under disease conditions. Amplification of the host and microbiome targeted genes in PCR, demonstrated feces contain EVs that are associated with DNA derived from the host and microbiome. AU: Amplification of bacterial 16s rRNA gene indicated that fEVs carry the bacterial DNA. These fEVs that carry bacterial-derived DNA could represent EVs secreted by gut bacteria or host derived EVs encapsulating bacterial DNA. Further investigations are required to determine the precise origin of this fEV-DNA.

Interestingly, fEV derived DNA did not respond to the PCR amplification of plant and nematode-specific target genes. In the current study, samples were collected from 10-d-old pre-weaned calves AU: managed under a very intensive management system, primarily nourished with milk and commercial milk replacer feed. Interestingly,

even the EV-DNA isolated from the feces of lactating cows showed no amplification of targets specific to plants. AU: Ponzoni et al. (2009) previously reported the amplification of chloroplast-based genes from green plants in cow milk, but this was only evident with higher quantities of total DNA (400 ng and 800 ng). The limited quantity of DNA present in fEVs could potentially explain the absence of amplification for the targeted plant gene. Furthermore, the animals in the current investigation were raised in a clean and hygienic environment and exhibited no clinical indications of nematode infections which explains negative amplification for genes specific for nematodes as well. The Bradford assay after the RIPA lysis of fEVs, and CBB staining of fEV-protein after SDS-PAGE, indicated that a considerable amount of protein cargo is also present in the fEV (Lerner et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2021). Furthermore, we have demonstrated the presence of a substantial amount of small RNAs in fEVs derived from the calf. EVs-enriched fractions contained both vesicular RNA as well as vesicles free RNA. However, according to previous studies, SEC isolates of EVs have the highest percentages of vesicular RNA and less of non-vesicular small RNA/miRNA contaminants in comparison to other available EV enrichment techniques (Northrop-Albrecht et al., 2022). Therefore, our current experimental data suggest that EVs isolated from pe-weaned calf feces harbor a substantial amount of RNA, suggesting their potential utility in disease diagnosis and monitoring specifically in terms of gene expression response.

Freezing and thawing of fecal samples could potentially lead to cell and microbe rupture within the sample, thereby promoting the release of additional vesicles (Trusal et al., 1984; Sivanantham and Jin, 2022). Potentially, larger particles including apoptotic bodies and non-vesicle particles in the sample could rupture into smaller ones within the EV size range. These factors may contribute to an increase in the concentration of nanoparticles in the samples (Kalamvoki and Deschamps, 2016; Shearn et al., 2020). In the current study, we observed this increment of nanoparticles in the samples stored at -80°C without any preprocessing compared with fresh or preprocessed-frozen samples. To mitigate the effect of freezing-thawing on EV enrichment, cells and larger particles present in the sample were removed before storing it at -80°C by following a preprocessing step. This showed that preprocessing effectively prevented the introduction of additional nanoparticles during the storage and freezing-thawing process, showing no significant disparity in particle concentration, size, or morphology between EVs enriched from preprocessed-stored samples and those from fresh samples. Hence, it is crucial to adopt the optimized method established in this study to ensure the accurate preservation of EVs, as evidenced by their

intact structure observed under TEM in EVs isolated from all 3 sample types.

In the data comparing the characteristics of fEVs isolated from feces of healthy vs *Cryptosporidium* positive calves, 2 main differences in size and the zeta potential of isolated fEVs were observed. There was a significant decrement in the average size of fEVs isolated from infected samples compared with healthy samples. AU: Previous studies have reported similar observations in various disease conditions, including cancers, liver diseases, neurodegenerative disorders, and infectious diseases, where an increase in the secretion of smaller-sized EVs, such as exosomes (Schorey and Harding, 2016; Ipinmoroti and Matthews, 2020). Accordingly, our observation of presenting a larger proportion of smaller-sized fEVs in *Cryptosporidium* infected samples may be attributed to increased secretion of smaller-sized EVs, such as exosomes, during the infection. Stimulation of exosome secretion during infection has the potential to increase the abundance of smaller vesicles in enriched EV samples from biological clinical specimens, particularly in diseased conditions as opposed to healthy states. Previous studies suggest that high secretion and circulation of exosomes play a role in their pathogenesis by promoting cell-cell and host-pathogen communication (Mathivanan et al., 2010). It is known that enteric pathogen infections such as *Cryptosporidium* spp. infections can cause alterations in gut microbiome composition and diversity, and activate the inflammatory response in addition to clinical symptoms such as diarrhea and mal-absorption (Dorbek-Kolin et al., 2022). All these factors account for the heterogeneity of fEV composition when comparing the isolated EV populations from the feces of healthy and infected animals. Thus it is imperative to perform additional investigations to elucidate the underlying factors contributing to the reduction in the average size of EVs derived from calf feces. Moreover, with the recent advancements in microfluidics based EV purifications and characterizations, there is a prospective utility of these alterations in the development of diagnostic, prognostic, and monitoring tools for disease assessment.

To date, no evidence links infectious disease diagnosis and monitoring with the ZP of EVs isolated from clinical samples. However, a study conducted by (Mendivil-Alvarado et al., 2023) explains the association of the ZP of plasma-derived EVs with the biomarkers of metabolic risk and disease prognosis in women with breast cancer. The findings of our study revealed a significant difference in the zeta potential values of EVs isolated from *Cryptosporidium*-infected samples compared with healthy samples. According to our results, EVs isolated from the healthy group are larger and exhibit a high negative ZP value compared with smaller EVs isolated from the infected group. This alteration in ZP value

might be due to differences in size and the composition of the membrane of the EVs derived from these 2 groups. This is supported by the study by (Matsumura et al., 2019) which demonstrated that EVs derived from tumor cells, characterized by low-density and larger diameter, possess a more negative zeta potential in comparison to the small-sized, high-density EVs. If the size difference arises from presenting a higher proportion of exosomes in the infected samples, the difference in ZP values could potentially be due to variations in the biogenesis processes of vesicles and their size difference. In addition to that, recent studies have shown that the ZP value of isolated EVs can be changed with the cell type (Akagi et al., 2014; Jamaludin et al., 2019). Therefore, additional comprehensive studies are warranted to elucidate the precise factors contributing to the significant difference observed in the ZP values of EVs isolated from infected and healthy samples.

The overall evidence from the current study suggest that fEVs of sufficient purity can be enriched from pre-weaned calf feces using the described protocol which has a potential of biomonitoring or diagnostic/prognostics values due to their molecular cargo including protein, DNA, and RNA. These components can serve as valuable resources for the development of tools aimed at investigating gut physiology, pathophysiology, and host-pathogen interactions in the context of gut infections. Differences in the size and ZP value of fEVs isolated from healthy and diseased cohorts could be a potential marker for distinguishing between EVs obtained from healthy and diseased individuals in future studies. Moreover, in future studies, it would be interesting to analyze the proteomics, genomics, and transcriptomic changes of fEVs under healthy and disease states, providing valuable insights into their functional roles and diagnostic potential.

In the current study, all the fecal samples were collected from Holstein Friesian calves, the most abundant cattle breed in Estonia. Hence repeating the same under different management conditions, breeds, age groups, and diseases would help in validating our findings.

CONCLUSION

We were able to devise a protocol for the enrichment of fEVs from calf feces with minimal contaminants and demonstrated the presence of protein, DNA, and RNA cargo in fEVs. EVs isolated from the feces of *Cryptosporidium* infected animals are significantly smaller and less negative in zeta potential compared with EVs isolated from the feces of healthy animals indicating the possibility of used them as putative biomarkers with futher field studies. This observation underscores that pathogenic infections significantly influence the general character-

istics of fEVs. Thus, fEVs can be used with available assay platforms to detect early biomarkers and also can be used to understand host-pathogen interaction, microbial diversity, dysbiosis, or even the origin of the EVs with additional investigations as a non-invasive tool.

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Ethics statement All experimental protocols involving animals in this study were reviewed and approved by the Ethical Committee of Animal Experiments of the Estonian Ministry of Agriculture (animal project permit no. 116)

Conflict of interests The authors have not stated any conflicts of interest.

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Availability of data and materials The data that support the findings of this study are available from the first and corresponding author, upon reasonable request.

Authors' contributions Conceptualization, C.P., T.O., S.K. and A.F.; Formal analysis, C.P., T.O., S.K., and A.F.; Funding acquisition, A.F., T.O., S.K.; Investigation, C.P., G.M., K.G., T.O., S.K., and A.F.; Methodology, C.P., G.M., K.G., A.A., T.O., S.K. and A.F.; Project administration, A.F.; Resources, A.A., T.O., and A.F.; Supervision, T.O., S.K. and A.F.; Visualization, C.P., A.A., S.K.; Writing—original draft, C.P.; Writing—review and editing, C.P., G.M., K.G., Q.R., T.O., S.K. and A.F.

Abbreviations: BCV Bovine coronavirus, **dSEC:** Double size exclusion chromatography, **EVs:** Extracellular vesicles, **fEVs:** Faecal extracellular vesicles, **NTA:** Nanoparticle tracking analysis, **SEC:** Size exclusion chromatography, **SEM:** Standard error of the mean, **sSEC:** Single size exclusion chromatography, **TEM:** Transmission electron microscopy, **WB:** Western blotting, **ZP:** Zeta Potential,

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